

FORMATION OF A YOUNG SPECIALIST THROUGH THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-ESTEEM**Prozorova M.***Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences
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The purpose of the study is to determine the features and direction of the influence of professional self-esteem on the formation of young professionals. The article clarifies the theoretical justification of the importance of professional self-assessment in the system of secondary vocational education. The study analyzes the changes and aspects of professional education, the growing requirements for a modern specialist, as well as the features of the professional development of a competitive student, which in turn is impossible without the formation of a professional assessment of his personality. The scientific novelty of the research lies in the description of the current directions of the formation of professional self-esteem.

As a result, it is proved that for the formation of professional self-esteem in a young specialist, it is necessary to create pedagogical conditions.

Keywords: professional self-assessment; professional self-determination; professional activity; young specialist; motivation of achievements.

The relevance of the studied issue is fixed by the lack of coping skills of the identified difficulties, as well as the formation of the expected professional and personal self-esteem of students in the educational and professional environment of secondary vocational education institutions. Based on the need to find ways to become a young specialist, we came to the conclusion that improving the professional competence of future specialists is possible through critical analysis.

The purpose of our work is to study the influence of professional self-esteem on the formation of young professionals.

This research is applied, since the curriculum is aimed at forming an active professional and personal position of students. The main idea of our research is the theoretical justification of the organization of educational programs in specialized educational institutions, which makes educational and professional interaction between teachers and students a condition for changing self-esteem.

In this regard, there are serious changes in the professional education of future specialists, which are associated with the need for intellectual and behavioral flexibility. It is necessary to focus not only on professionalism, but also on personality, to increase self-awareness and interest in self-improvement, to develop a holistic personality [1]. The modernization of society and the growing demand for young professionals today determine the importance of the academic environment for solving the problems of self-development and professional development of competitive professionals, which is impossible without a proper assessment of a person's personality and professional potential.

In this regard, serious changes in the professional education of specialists who need a competent career, as well as people-oriented doctors, increase interest in self-knowledge and self-development, forming full-fledged personalities. Improving the quality of modern society and the growing needs of modern young professionals are prioritized among professionals in determining the problem of personal growth and professional

development of competitive specialists, which is very difficult without a timely assessment of their direction and professional potential.

The world of professions is very big. It covers thousands of different and interesting specialties. Different professions require different and sometimes contradictory characteristics.

The social value of a person, his status among others, job satisfaction, physical and mental health, well-being and carelessness depend on how well his life path is chosen. Professional activity is one of the main indicators, the most important aspects in the life of a future professional. Human professions are very diverse and, according to psychologists and educators, most of these professions can be mastered by everyone. But it is equally true that a person can complete a task at once, and life is limited, so a young person masters several professions at once in order to be competitive and in demand in the labor market, in modern reality. Because in fact, it is difficult for a young specialist to keep up with the changes that occur taking into account technological and economic progress, hence the question of choosing and mastering another profession arises [5, p. 138].

The theoretical basis of the research is the analysis of personal self-esteem, which is studied in the scientific works of the largest teachers and psychologists who have made a serious contribution to the study of theoretical approaches (B.G. Ananyev, R. Burns, L.I. Bozhovich, W. James, F. Zimbardo, V. Quinn, I.S. Cohn, A.N. Leontiev, R. Meili, I.N. Mikheeva, V.V. Ovsyannikova, A.V. Petrovsky, S.L. Rubinstein, E.T. Sokolova, V.V. Stolin, A.G. Spirkin, P.R. Chamata, I.I. Chesnokova, T. Shibusani, etc.). The authors explore such provisions as the system, the possibility and patterns of proper self-assessment in the development of personality.

European and American scientists and educators believe that self-esteem is one of the most important mechanisms for regulating human communication with the outside world. Russian teachers and psychologists

describe that the formation of professional self-esteem is the main incentive for the growth of a person's creative potential, as well as helping to adapt as much as possible to changes in the social environment [5, p. 196].

The analysis of literary sources on research issues made it possible to emphasize to some extent the relevant directions:

- self-assessment affects independent qualified activities that are in demand among specialists (B.G. Ananyev, L.I. Bozhovich, I.S. Kohn, V.V. Stolin, J. Mead, F. Perls, etc.), in the research works of the above authors, attention is paid to the relationship between self-esteem, "self-image" and "I am the concept" of a developing person. Self-esteem in a particular case is considered by us as a mechanism for the formation of the above-mentioned aspects;

- the relationship between the motivation to achieve actions and self-esteem (J. Atkinson, D. McClelland, N. Feather, X. Heckhausen, K. Schneider, etc.), ultimately, in the description of the presented concept of "achievement motivation", the position of each author was tracked, as a result, a difference was found in the assessment of the role and value of self-esteem in professional activity of students. Some studies have allowed us to consider the scientific basis for studying the formation of proper professional self-esteem.

The main part

Professional self-assessment is a practice-oriented resource analysis of young people, which allows them to determine their position in the professional environment with their skills and competencies, qualities and achievements as competent specialists. As A.A. Rean writes, "Professional self-esteem is one of the structural components of the professional concept of "I am a professional", which includes the working and personal aspects. The corresponding change is expressed in the assessment of personality qualities associated with the presentation of the image of "I am an expert". The corresponding changes are expressed as an assessment of personality qualities associated with the concept of the "I" image. In this case, professional self-assessment may differ from the final and potential self-assessment" [7, p. 214].

Accidentally, a high or low self-esteem of a specialist often does not contribute at all to the productive development of his career, but is a consequence of the qualities that a specialist faces: doubts, distrust, arrogance, aggression, anxiety and nervousness. Low professional self-esteem is an indicator that negatively affects the change and effectiveness of a certified specialist.

This trend is less noticeable among young professionals with a professional education. With the qualification and growth of professional potential, future specialists develop their own image of professional advancement in modern conditions. When choosing professional assignments and assessing competencies, young specialists are guided by past practical or work experience, and unstable emotional components are expressed in stressful and difficult life situations, as a result of which this leads to a situation of failure [7, p. 328].

For the most part, self-esteem becomes paramount in the formation of many professionally important qualities. For example, risks are often caused by low self-esteem. Self-assessment in combination with the overall performance assessment process can have significant benefits for the employer, young professionals and the organization as a whole.

The formed self-assessment allows you to expand the participation of professionals in the evaluation process and achieve personal results. This strategy of self-assessment development is combined with the formation of a holistic program aimed at evaluating a young specialist in relation to professional goals. The advantage of including a self-assessment system in the educational program of an educational institution is the experience of evaluating a future professional, which makes it possible to see real or imaginary shortcomings of their own activities [6].

S.L. Rubinstein wrote that a real person reflected in his consciousness is perceived as "I" as the subject of his activity. He stressed that a person is primarily determined by his attitude to work. Thus, his self-esteem is determined by what he does for society as a member of society. S.L. Rubinstein said that self-esteem is "the core of personal self-consciousness" [8, p. 254].

In the modern professional community, a specialist with low self-esteem is not perceived by anyone, perhaps except his mentor. Since no one knows better than himself, it is therefore easy to notice that uncertainty is a kind of signal to others for help in professional development.

Self-esteem is important, because a person has firm confidence in his professional and personal ways, confidence in what is happening, confidence in the adequacy of what is happening. A high level of self-esteem is better achieved with an adequate realistic assessment of one's own capabilities. Insufficient self-esteem generates the usual helplessness - the young man is afraid of problems and troubles that arise because he can't do anything about it [6].

It is interesting to observe self-esteem in practice, which determines the level of claim. A high level of claims indicates that a person strives to achieve great success in the professional world. The current situation makes it possible to determine his social and professional level and take his place in professional development. These circumstances push the young specialist to the fact that he is ready to take risks and perform complex tasks. Low-level statements arise from people for whom the main value is not to lose what has been achieved in order to avoid failure.

Professional development is an individual and complex process consisting of four stages:

- 1) evolution of general professional competencies;
- 2) professional development;
- 3) General socio-psychological adaptation;
- 4) selective or complete self-realization of a future competent specialist in the course of work.

E.F. Zeer compares professional character formation with human labor activity, taking into account the term "progressive personality change under the influence of social factors, professional activity and am-

ateur activity aimed at self-improvement and self-realization." The scientist invests in professional formation the following concept of "personal development in the process of choosing a profession, vocational education, as well as productive performance of professional activity" [2, p. 128].

N.V. Matolygina Ph.D. in her research suggests that professional formation is a flexible personality trait that combines an adequate assessment of professional activity, influencing the process of personal and professional development, as well as education and readiness for professional maturation in a career. At the same time, the author emphasizes that professional development in modern conditions requires improvement, transformation in one's life, self-realization as a person [4, p. 46].

We share the opinion of A.K. Markova about professional development as a productive process of personal development and self-realization. Many studies on this issue are aimed at the independent organization of a person's professional activity and self-determination in the professional market, which as a result leads to career self-realization and possible potential for achieving high career growth [3, p. 47].

From the point of view of A.K. Markova, professional development of a person contributes to the development of the spirit, saturates a person's life with an important meaning, gives importance to a professional particle [3, p. 94]. In our opinion, the emerging difficulty in the development of the professional formation of young professionals lies in the awareness of not all students of the important goal of their future professional education. Many of them enter professional educational institutions, guided by the choice of some not so important parameters:

- the choice of parents of professional educational institutions;
- there is no competition for admission to educational institutions;
- there are no entrance exams to educational institutions;
- conveniently located educational institutions.

We believe that the development of the professional potential of young professionals depends entirely on the factors:

- advanced knowledge, skills, practical experience of teaching the content of educational institutions, the results of classes contribute to the development of general professional competence;
- self-organization of students in the learning process, as well as in the conditions of industrial practice.

Thus, the work of the teacher is aimed at encouraging students to show their professional competencies at a deeper, more conscious level of personality.

Teachers, in turn, must consistently develop in order to become qualified professionals in their field and be of interest to their students. This requires timely participation in advanced training courses, various internships, participation in professional competitions and gaining experience. This makes it possible to comprehensively assess education and emerging situations in conditions of fierce competition. Many subject teachers

experience a decrease in students' motivation, which usually affects their attitude to the subject.

To solve this problem, and in particular to motivate students to study, various practice-oriented formats and methods are used in the professional environment of the college to maximize the involvement of each student and create interesting lectures and practices. The forms of such educational activities are trips of various kinds, master classes, professional exhibitions and competitions.

In the professional development of a young professional, his high motivation and interest in the educational process depends on the application of practice-oriented forms and methods of teaching.

Conclusion

Professional results are always internal decisions of a person, not external reasons. In other words, the system of secondary vocational education has everything that helps a student to succeed. These internal and sometimes closed signs that distinguish a successful person from an unsuccessful one consist mainly of three components: self-esteem, sociability and energy. Confidence gives a person the opportunity to deal with what he already considers unacceptable, and gives him new opportunities. High self-esteem helps to avoid delays in choosing a behavior model. Successful people follow a strategic direction, choosing it, moving without stopping. He knows that other paths will lead to the achievement of a professional goal, but his confidence lies in the fact that the path he has chosen is no worse than any other, and he is confident that he will reach a high point of development. Healthy ambitions and the desire to be the best motivate young professionals and their chosen organization to move forward [9, p. 112].

In addition, it should be noted that this requires the creation of pedagogical conditions in the college curriculum, including the formation of students' professional and personal self-esteem:

- the structure of educational activities focused on identifying students' personal resources;
- promoting student cohesion in the microenvironment;
- helping students solve difficult life situations during their studies, and building relationships with classmates;
- application of development methods and game equipment in the training program for specialists of secondary vocational training.

Support in the educational environment is aimed at creating a positive atmosphere in the college's educational program, as well as psychological support for students, which, as a rule, makes it possible to develop professional self-esteem and lead it to personal and career growth.

We see the prospects for further research in a deeper study of educational and professional activities in the conditions of the formation of a professional and personal assessment of oneself as a young purposeful specialist. It seems to us that this will allow us to streamline the process, the consequence of which is the formation of professional self-esteem determined by educational conditions: self-awareness; the choice of the most appropriate languages in professional work

and the creation of interpersonal communications; increasing the possibilities of training and development of self-learning functions, creating a micro and macro professional environment based on experience; individual interpersonal communication.

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